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HISTORY OF THE VETERINARY SERVICE OF THE PEOPLE OF TURKISTAN IN HISTORICAL SOURCES

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Abstract: The independence of our Motherland created an opportunity to objectively study and present the past of our people based on historical sources. In particular, special attention has been given to the study of invaluable sources concerning the veterinary service of our people, who have traditionally been engaged in animal husbandry. These sources include archaeological findings that survived the harsh trials of time, the most ancient stone inscriptions, manuscripts, and more than twenty thousand written documents. The scientific study and research of these materials, as well as presenting them to specialists in the field of veterinary medicine, have significant educational importance. Knowledge of the history of veterinary services among the peoples of Uzbekistan greatly influences the further development of the field and serves as a powerful means in shaping modern veterinarians as highly moral, dedicated, responsible, and patriotic professionals.

Keywords: veterinary service, folk medicine, archival materials, peoples of Central Asia, Turkestan region, livestock, historical source, infectious diseases.

When studying the history of our Motherland objectively and scientifically on the basis of historical sources, we also carry out significant work in researching the history of veterinary medicine among our people, who have traditionally possessed abundant livestock, and in educating devoted specialists of this field in the spirit of patriotism. During scientific research it has been revealed in many historical sources that veterinary science and medicine developed in close harmony, and that our ancient pastoral people were highly skilled masters of their profession.

In the Turkestan region and, in general, in the territories of Central Asia, by the second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, veterinary services entered a new stage of development characterized by a unique feature: their integration with folk medicine. This period is distinguished by its important historical progress.

According to historical sources, in the second half of the nineteenth century Europe, Russia, and Asian regions, including Central Asia and Afghanistan, experienced epidemiological outbreaks and especially epizootic infectious diseases. In order to eliminate and prevent these diseases, states were forced to cooperate with each other. In particular, the Russian Empire had to reach agreements with the Khiva and Bukhara Khanates. Between 1801 and 1860 various infectious epizootic diseases occurred across Russia, Europe, and Asia, causing significant economic losses to these countries and to livestock farming in the region.

During these years, especially dangerous infectious diseases affecting livestock became widespread. Among them were anthrax, plague-like cattle diseases, rinderpest, contagious pleuropneumonia, rabies, foot-and-mouth disease, sheep pox, glanders in horses, and other poorly understood veterinary diseases. These diseases caused serious damage to livestock breeding in the regions mentioned above.

According to data from the Russian State Statistical Administration, these infectious diseases also spread among the population and turned into epidemics. It was reported that until the 1870s neither livestock nor humans were effectively cured of these diseases.

Furthermore, information from the Russian Ministry of Internal Affairs indicates that during the years 1837, 1844–1845, 1847–1849, and 1852, epizootic outbreaks—primarily cattle plague, rinderpest, and anthrax—resulted in the death of 3.6 million head of large livestock and horses. According to data from the Ministry of State

Property of Russia, between 1844 and 1848 about 3 million animals died. Information from the Department of Imperial Estates reports that between 1833–1840, 1842–1846, and 1852–1860, nearly 300,000 agricultural animals perished.

The total economic damage caused by epizootic infectious diseases was enormous. According to the Russian Ministry of Internal Affairs, losses in 1841 alone amounted to 1 million rubles. The Ministry of State Property reported that livestock farming losses caused by epizootic diseases reached 1.7 million rubles in 1848 and 3.2 million rubles in 1849.

At the end of the nineteenth century, a widespread infectious disease in South America destroyed almost the entire cattle population: out of 9 million head of cattle, only a few hundred remained alive. Similarly, as a result of cattle plague in France, between 1713 and 1746, about 11 million head of cattle died. In Italy, between 1794 and 1797, about 4 million animals perished. In Germany, during the eighteenth century and the first half of the nineteenth century, 28 million cattle died due to similar diseases. Historical documents confirm that in Russia, over a period of 26 years (1881–1906), 3.5 million head of cattle were lost due to such diseases.

Central Asia also experienced zoonanthroponotic diseases, similar to those in Russia, which caused serious damage to both livestock farming and the human population. However, neither the Khiva Khanate nor the Bukhara Emirate provided official reports about these outbreaks. Evidence confirming that such epizootic infectious diseases also occurred in the region can be found in the monograph “My Beloved History” by the historian G. A. Hidayatov. In this work it is mentioned that in the 1870s a strange disease in Central Asia damaged silkworms and almost destroyed sericulture.

In the region, epizootic infectious diseases and zoonanthroponotic illnesses were studied as a component of general medical science. Traditional veterinary practices

initially focused on proper livestock care, good feeding, and strict adherence to zoosanitary and zoohygienic requirements. Shepherds, horse keepers, farriers, and livestock caretakers treated animal diseases following the recommendations and works of prominent representatives of folk medical knowledge. At the same time, they benefited from the scientific heritage of our ancestors who made great contributions to human civilization.

Information related to veterinary practice can also be found in several written sources. For example, the preface of “Boznoma” (The Book of the Falcon) written by Ahmad Khoja Tarkhon states that it was composed as a manual for Sheikh Khoja Muhammad Karim, the son of Muhammad Shah Abdul Fattah, who was passionate about hunting. The work is an encyclopedic guide describing hunting birds, their characteristics, differences between males and females, the diseases affecting them, and methods of treatment. The manuscript was copied in Hijri 1266 (1850 CE).

Another treatise entitled “On the Healing Properties of Animal Bodies”, whose author is unknown, describes the medicinal use of different parts of animals and insects to treat diseases and even prevent misfortunes. The Holy Qur’an also contains references to animals. It mentions the creation of pairs of sheep, goats, camels, and cattle and animals that carry loads and those used for food.

The purpose of citing these examples from the sacred book is to show that our pastoral people paid great attention to preserving the health of animals granted by God and protecting livestock from diseases that could bring disaster to animal husbandry and the wealth of the people.

There were several reasons why the Russian imperial authorities became seriously interested in livestock breeding and the animal world of Central Asia. Central Asia has a hot and dry climate favorable for livestock breeding. The region possesses vast pastures, meadows, and foothill valleys suitable for animal husbandry. Livestock products were

an important commodity in domestic and foreign trade and were in demand on the world market. Many pathogens harmful to livestock are destroyed under strong sunlight, while in Russia livestock often died from epizootic and parasitic diseases.

For these reasons the Russian Empire sought to develop veterinary services in the region in order to benefit economically from livestock production. For example, between 1888 and 1908, 1,030,417 animals died from anthrax out of 1,286,637 infected animals in Russia. Other infectious diseases such as foot-and-mouth disease, tuberculosis, and glanders also caused serious economic losses. According to statistical data, in Turkestan there were 19,208,000 head of livestock in 1900 and 21,681,000 head in 1910. Among them in 1910 there were 16,625,000 sheep and goats, 2,152,000 cattle, 2,023,000 camels, and 80,000 donkeys.

Livestock and livestock products were an important source of income for the region, although a significant portion of this wealth was appropriated by the colonial authorities of the Russian Empire. According to historical statistical data, the income obtained by Russia from Turkestan between 1869 and 1896 amounted to 158 million rubles in the currency of that period.

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